

Introduction: Space based solar power (SBSP) has been conceptualised since the 1960s as a method of converting solar radiation captured by an orbiting satellite into electricity for transmission [3]. International interest in long-term lunar exploration continues to grow, as outlined in the Global Space Exploration Roadmap [5], and establishing a consistently manned lunar settlement requires reliable power generation.

Generating power on the lunar surface presents challenges due to the 14-day lunar night and low sun angle, meaning panels would have to be mounted on poles. In addition, lunar dust can degrade solar panel performance through obscuring sunlight and electrostatic charging, and may interfere with electrical connectors. Concepts such as lunar surface solar farms and nuclear fission systems have been proposed [1,2], however nuclear systems generate additional complexity in launch and construction. Space based solar power generation offers an alternative approach. Power can be transmitted using microwave power transmission (MPT), which converts direct current from solar cells into microwave energy for reception by a rectenna [8].

Near Rectilinear Halo Orbits (NRHOs), associated with the Earth-Moon L1 and L2 families of halo orbits, have been identified as favourable for cislunar missions due to their orbital stability and reduced eclipse exposure [9]. The highly elliptical nature of the NRHO results in extended dwell times at apoapsis, increasing access duration while maintaining favourable illumination conditions. This study aims to determine the optimum lunar orbit for solar power generation and transmission to a lunar south pole base by comparing Near Rectilinear Halo Orbits with circular and elliptical lunar orbits.

Methodology: Orbital simulations were conducted using Ansys Systems Tool Kit (STK) over one

lunar synodic month (29 days, 12 hours, 44 minutes and 3 seconds) [6]. Five different lunar orbits were compared:

- Lunar Gateway’s Near Rectilinear Halo Orbit (NRHO)
- A 100 km altitude circular orbit
- A 3000 km altitude circular orbit
- A 1000 km apoapsis elliptical orbit
- A 3000 km apoapsis elliptical orbit

All non NRHO orbits had an inclination of 90° to ensure visibility to the lunar south pole base. The NRHO was modelled by importing SPK trajectory data made available by NASA’s Jet Propulsion Laboratory into STK’s SPICE propagator [7]. The additional circular and elliptical orbits were modelled using STK’s orbit design tools.

A simplified satellite model was used across all orbits. A lunar base was modelled as a facility object at the lunar south pole, located between the Shackleton and De Gerlache craters (-89.684° latitude, 163.261° longitude). A 60° field of view sensor was attached to the base to represent the rectenna used for microwave power transmission, derived from prior SBSP studies [4].

Access analysis was performed to determine transmission opportunities between the satellite and the lunar base. The solar power generated was calculated using STK’s Solar Panel Tool, taking account of solar incidence angle, solar intensity, solar panel area and efficiency (derived from the satellite model). Power generation was computed at 30-minute intervals for each orbit over the duration of the synodic month.

Results: The highest power was generated by the Lunar Gateway NRHO, which generated 4,489,058 W cumulative power over the synodic month. This was 21.9% greater than the next best performing configuration, the 3000 km elliptical orbit (3,683,546 W).

Figure 1: Visualisation of the chosen orbits. [Image: Ansys STK]

The 1000 km elliptical orbit produced 3,680,360 W, and the 3000 km circular orbit produced 3,448,278 W. The 100 km circular orbit generated 2,734,908 W and experienced 255 eclipse events, significantly reducing its overall performance.

In terms of transmission opportunities, the NRHO provided the longest cumulative access time at 673.08 hours across five access periods. The 3000 km circular orbit provided 163 hours across 87 access periods, and the 3000 km elliptical orbit provided 99 hours across 88 access periods. The 1000 km elliptical orbit provided 43 hours across 199 access periods. The 100 km circular orbit produced the highest number of access events (361), but the average access duration was only 3.29 minutes, with a total access duration of only 20 hours.

The results indicate that orbital geometry plays a significant role in SBSP performance. While lower altitude circular orbits offer frequent access opportunities, their short duration and high eclipse frequency reduce suitability for lunar SBSP applications.

The highly elliptical nature of the NRHO enables extended dwell time over the lunar south pole, resulting in longer cumulative access time while maintaining high power generation. The NRHO exhibited only one eclipse event during the simulation period. The results align with prior research identifying favourable stability and communication characteristics of NRHOs for lunar missions [9].

Discussion and Further Work: The maximum gap between NRHO access periods was 9 hours 6 minutes and 37 seconds. It was assumed that the lunar base could store power received during access periods to maintain operation between transmission windows.

Several limitations apply to the design of this study. The simulation period of one lunar synodic month was selected as a trade-off between computational feasibility and obtaining meaningful comparative performance results, as longer simulations would capture the effects of the 18.6-year lunar nodal cycle on orbital behaviour. Perturbations were not included in the modelling, and a limited number of orbital configurations were analysed. Transmission feasibility was assumed based on line-of-sight access between the satellite and the lunar base rectenna. In addition, detailed local terrain effects at the base were not included in the access analysis, so the terrain surrounding the rectenna was not assumed to block the field of view. The lunar south pole location for the base was selected due to its relevance to planned lunar exploration missions and the presence of regions of extended illumination near the Shackleton crater. The analysis also used a standard satellite model (Skynet 5) rather than a purpose designed SBSP system.

Further work should extend simulations over longer durations of time to assess the long-term orbital behaviour, including the effects of perturbations. Additional analysis should also consider alternative

base locations, and the effect of orbit on the choice of lunar base location due to transmission requirements. Multi satellite configurations should be considered as an alternative, alongside the use of purpose built and designed SBSP satellites, including larger solar array areas for increased power generation, dedicated MPT systems and configurations optimised for continuous pointing towards the rectenna. Transmission system performance should also be considered in future work, including pointing to the rectenna and station keeping budgets should be assessed through ΔV requirements. The feasibility of in orbit construction and deployment should also be considered as the in-orbit service and manufacturing industry continues to grow.

Conclusions: This study presents a comparative analysis of Near Rectilinear Halo Orbits, circular and elliptical lunar orbits for space based solar power delivery to a lunar south pole base. The study demonstrates how orbital geometry directly impacts power generation within a consistent modelling approach. The Lunar Gateway NRHO was identified as the most effective orbital configuration among those analysed for solar power generation and transmission. The NRHO produced the highest cumulative power and provided the longest total access time over one synodic month. Lower altitude circular orbits were limited by frequent eclipse events and short transmission windows, while elliptical and higher altitude circular orbits provided intermediate performance.

Further work should extend simulations beyond one lunar synodic month to evaluate long-term stability and performance. Specialised satellite designs for lunar SBSP applications should also be considered, with larger solar array areas for increased power generation, dedicated MPT systems and configurations optimised for continuous rectenna pointing.

References: [1] Burke J. D. (1985) Lunar Bases and Space Activities of the 21st Century, 77. [2] Elliott J. O., Reh K. and MacPherson D. (2006) Lunar fission surface power system design and implementation concept, AIP Conf. Proc., 813, 942–952. [3] Glaser P. E. (1969) Satellite solar power station. *Solar Energy*, 12, 353–361. [4] Goh S. T., Zekavat S. A. and Abdelkhalik O. (2015) LEO satellite formation for SSP: energy and doppler analysis. *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, 51, 18–30. [5] Hufenbach B. et al. (2015) International missions to lunar vicinity and surface-near-term mission scenario of the global space exploration roadmap. IAF 66th Int. Astronautical Congress, 1–11. [6] NASA (2017) Eclipses and the Moon's Orbit. [7] NASA (2018) NAIF SPICE Ephemeris Data Archive. [8] Sasaki S., Tanaka K. and Maki K. I. (2013) Microwave power transmission technologies for solar power satellites. *Proc. IEEE*, 101, 1438–1447. [9] Zimovan E. M., Howell K. C. and Davis D. C. (2017) Near rectilinear halo orbits and their application in cislunar space., 20, 40.